

Wetland restoration for the future - ALFAwetlands

Tuula Larmola¹, Tuula Aalto², Erik Andersson³, Juraj Balkovic⁴, Alex Barthelmes⁵, Kris Decler⁶, Emmi Haltia¹, Kaido Soosaar⁷, Andis Ladzins⁸, Josep Peñuelas⁹, Jan Peters⁵, Maud Raman¹⁰, Max Rossberg¹¹, Francesc Sabater¹², José Miguel Sánchez Pérez¹³, Iryna Shchoka¹¹, Julien Tournebize¹⁴, Elise Vitali¹⁵, Liisa Ukonmaanaho¹

¹Natural Resources Institute Finland, Finland. ²Finnish Meteorological Institute, Finland.

³Stockholm University, Sweden. ⁴International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria.

⁵Michael Succow Foundation, Germany. ⁶Society for Ecological Restoration Europe, Belgium.

⁷University of Tartu, Estonia. ⁸Latvian State Forest Research Institute Silava, Latvia. ⁹Ecological & Forestry Applications Research Centre, Spain. ¹⁰Research Institute Nature & Forest, Belgium.

¹¹European Wilderness Society, Austria. ¹²University of Barcelona, Spain. ¹³French National Centre for Scientific Research, France. ¹⁴National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food & Environment, France.

¹⁵Wetlands International, Netherlands

Abstract

The European Union (EU) aims to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by at least 55% by 2030. This requires new GHG mitigation measures within all sectors, including Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector. Sustainable management and restoration of carbon (C) rich ecosystems, such as wetlands, may efficiently contribute to both EU's climate targets and biodiversity by providing cost-efficient climate change mitigation, maintaining biodiversity and water-related services, as well as providing income for landowners. Engagement of local communities in sustainable use and protection of wetlands is highly relevant for enabling transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society across EU. However, significant gaps prevail on wetlands' spatial extent, their magnitude as C sinks and sources, and sustainable restoration measures. This hinders the implementation of efficient C mitigation and adaptation measures in wetlands. ALFAwetlands (www.alfawetlands.eu), a Horizon Europe project (2022–2026), will advance the geospatial knowledge base of wetlands, evaluate pathways of wetland restoration that incorporate a co-creation process, and provide information to maximize climate change, biodiversity and other ecosystem benefits. A wide range of wetlands across Europe will be covered, including floodplains, coastal and artificial wetlands and peatlands. Boreal drained peatland forests and their management options (continuous cover forestry and ecological restoration) will be one of the foci in Estonia, Finland, and Latvia. At the local level, Living Labs support interdisciplinary research on ecological, environmental, economic, and social issues. Models will be used to explore the potential impacts of upscaled wetland restoration options on biodiversity and ecosystem services (BES) provision, as well as changes in BES provision at the EU level for various policy-relevant periods for both climate change mitigation and biodiversity targets. We will assess the socio-economic impacts of wetland restoration, especially on BES benefits and costs of different measures and wellbeing impacts from local to EU levels.

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